

Disease resistance

were used as checks. BR5 has fine aromatic grains. BR7 has long nonaromatic grains; Kataribhog has long aromatic grains but unsatisfactory yield.

Most of the lines varied widely in the visual scores — only 15 were scored 3 to 5 and none were scored 1. Fifty lines scored 7 and 54 lines, 9. Variability was observed for all characters studied. The table lists 15 selections equivalent to or better than the standard checks. All of the selected lines had numerically higher elongation-ratio values than the checks. But 12 selections had similar or higher imbibition ratio values, and most were equivalent to the checks in visual scores. ■

Elongation ratio, imbibition ratio, and visual score of selected aromatic IR424 lines. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1978.

Pedigree	Elongation ratio	Imbibition ratio	Visual score ^a
IR424-2-1			
/J1-30-6	2.00	3.98	3
/J1-30-7	1.98	3.95	3
/J1-30-8	1.88	3.76	3
/J7-2-4	1.85	3.69	3
/J7-2-5	1.75	3.77	3
/J7-2-7	1.85	2.61	5
/J7-2-9	1.85	3.69	3
/J7-2-15	1.85	2.74	5
/J7-4-11	1.76	2.52	5
/J7-4-14	1.82	3.62	3
/J7-4-15	2.00	4.31	3
/J8-1-8	2.07	4.47	3
/J8-1-9	2.00	3.98	3
/J8-1-18	2.01	4.35	3
/J8-7-14	1.88	4.07	3
BR5	1.70	3.58	3
BR7 ^b	1.40	3.60	3
Kataribhog	1.67	4.18	3

^a1 = All cooked grains smooth and uniform in length; 3 = 80% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 5 = 60% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 7 = 40% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 9 = 20% cooked grains smooth, uniform.

^bNonaromatic.

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Rice cultures that are moderately resistant to Helminthosporiose

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Helminthosporiose is widespread in Tamil Nadu. The disease affects the [rice crop at all growth stages; no cultivated variety is resistant or tolerant. The 540 IET entries received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for reaction to high pressure of helminthosporiose in a semidry nursery. The entries were grown in 2 rows, 1 In long, surrounded by 1 row of the susceptible check Benibhog. At 45 days of age the plants were spray inoculated with a conidial suspension (concn of 40,000 spores/ml) of *Helminthosporium oryzae* that had been isolated from typical lesions. The disease incidence was scored on a 0-9 scale. Benibhog had a score of 9 (highly susceptible) and many entries scored from 5 to 7. Five entries — IET5870, IET5878, IET6515, IET6524, and IET6541 — were scored from 0 to 1. When tested in the laboratory under similar inoculum pressure, the cultures showed moderate resistance to the disease (score, lower than 3). ■

Resistance of cultivars to the rice leaf folder

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Eleven standard cultivars and four promising lines were evaluated for resistance to the rice leaf folder in a randomized block design replicated three times in a field trial in 1977 kharif. In the last week of August, when leaf folder incidence was at a peak, all the leaves and those infested on 15 hills/replication

were counted and the percentage of infestation was recorded.

Infestation ranged from 13 to 63%; it was highest on Jaya and lowest on Prasad (see table). No cultivar was immune to leaf folder attack. ■

Susceptibility of rice cultivars to the rice leaf folder. Pantnagar, India.

Designation	Av infestation (%)
Jaya	63
IR8	61
Padma	57
UPR190D-17-1	55
IR20	52
UPR173-23	49
UPR82-1-7	49
Cauvery	42
Bala	38
Saket-4	36
Tilak chandan (dwarf (mutant))	31
Ratna	30
Pusa 2-21	24
IR24	15
Prasad	13
CD at 5%	17.55

Straighthead disease of rice suspected in southern Thailand

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Severe symptoms similar to those of straighthead disease reported in the USA and Japan were observed in southern Thailand in 1977. The observations were made in an 80-ha area of lowland rice planted on sandy soil that was previously planted to upland crops in Ronphibool subprovince, Nakornsrithamaraj province. The rice plants were at the heading stage. The infected plants had normal vegetative growth but exhibited tillering at the upper nodes, poor exertion, twisted spikelets, distorted hulls (in "parrot beak" shape), and high sterility.

To observe if varietal reactions to the disease differed, four replications of three recommended varieties, Nahng Prayah 132, RD13, and RD7, and of the local variety Khao Nang were randomly planted in the area in 1978 wet season. On the basis of the grain yield and the percentage of straighthead panicles, Khao Nang and Nahng Prayah 132 were more tolerant of straighthead disease than RD7 and RD13 (see table). To the authors' knowledge, this is the first report of straighthead symptoms in Southeast Asia. ■

Percentage of affected panicles and grain yield of 4 varieties as a measure of damage from straighthead disease (av of 4 replications). Nakornsrithamaraj Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

Variety	Straighthead panicles ^a (%)	Grain yield ^a (g/m ²)
Khao Nang	16 a	294 a
Nahng Prayah 132	39 b	161 b
RD13	63 c	148 b
RD7	63 c	98 b

^a In a column, values followed by the same letter do not significantly differ at the 0.05% level.

Dirty panicle or glume discoloration of rice in Sierra Leone

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The *dirty panicle* or *discolored glume* syndrome of rice is found in practically all rice ecologic zones in Sierra Leone. The disorder may be limited to individual grains, but in severe cases almost the entire panicles, including the rachises, become discolored. When the disease strikes, yield losses may reach 50%.

Some fungi associated with the disorder were identified by the Commonwealth Mycological Institute, U.K., and locally from seed samples from an upland area near Rokupr. They were: *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Leptosphaeria* sp., *Phoma sorghina*, *Diplodiella oryzae*, *Alternaria* sp., and *Fusarium* sp. Rice bugs that feed on grain also predispose the glumes to fungal infection.

Screening tests to determine varietal reactions to grain and glume discoloration

were conducted at a dryland site at Makassa, near the Rokupr Rice Research Station, in the 1977–78 wet season. Cultivars that had 10% or fewer affected grains were classed as resistant. They included IRAT8, M1069-1-2, M50-4-2-2,

M133-6-1-2, IAC47, and LAC23. Cultivars with 25% or more of their grains severely affected were classified as susceptible. They included IB96, IB100, Line 13d/R75 sel. 958, TOX C1-95-2-2-69-1, IAC5544, and Perola. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Field reaction of rice varieties to leaf folder at various nitrogen levels

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The rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, previously a minor rice pest in the Punjab, has lately become serious. In 1978 kharif, 16 varieties were screened for reaction to leaf folder at 6 nitrogen levels in 3 nitrogen variety trials: NVT 1 (short-duration varieties, 110 – 120 days), NVT 2 (medium duration, 135 – 145 days), and NVT 3 (aromatic varieties,

120 – 140 days).

In NVT 1, leaf folder infestation increased with increasing nitrogen level. Infestation was maximum in variety PR422 and minimum in Palman 579. In NVT 3, infestation did not increase consistently with increased nitrogen level. Damage was maximum in PR299B and minimum in PR106. In NVT 3, leaf folder infestation was significantly lower in plots that received less nitrogen. PR476 had maximum insect damage and PR484, minimum. Leaf folders generally preferred fine-grained, scented varieties to short and medium-duration, nonaromatic varieties. ■

Incidence of rice leaf folder on varieties at various nitrogen levels. Kapurthala, India, 1978.

Variety	Leaf folder-damaged leaves ^a (no./ 10 hills)						Mean
	0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha	
<i>NVT 1^b, short-duration varieties (110 – 120 days)</i>							
PR103	10.7	12.3	11.0	11.7	13.0	14.1	12.2
PR404	9.3	9.3	9.1	10.7	15.7	18.3	12.2
PR405	1.7	12.3	8.0	11.3	15.1	11.3	12.1
PR406	9.0	10.3	14.1	12.3	12.3	18.3	12.8
PR422	9.3	10.1	12.0	15.0	16.1	16.0	13.3
Palman 519	12.3	4.1	9.3	10.3	12.0	12.3	10.2
Mean	9.1	9.9	10.1	11.9	14.2	16.2	12.1
<i>NVT 2^c, medium-duration varieties (137 – 145 days)</i>							
PR106	1.0	1.0	8.7	7.5	6.0	10.7	6.8
PR299 A	1.3	4.0	8.5	10.0	11.3	8.3	8.2
PR299B	8.0	8.1	8.3	9.3	1.3	13.1	9.2
PR504	9.1	9.3	5.3	8.7	8.1	8.7	8.4
Jaya	5.7	7.8	9.5	9.0	5.3	8.0	7.6
Mean	1.5	6.2	8.1	8.9	1.7	9.9	8.0
<i>NVT 3^d, aromatic varieties (120 – 140 days)</i>							
PR214	11.0	14.3	28.1	33.1	38.0	42.3	28.0
PR431	10.7	12.0	23.1	21.1	34.1	41.3	25.0
PR416	18.0	21.3	21.0	29.0	32.3	41.1	28.2
PR484	10.3	14.0	11.1	19.0	34.1	39.3	22.5
Basmati 310	19.3	20.7	20.3	23.1	36.1	45.7	21.1
Mean	13.9	16.5	22.3	26.6	35.3	43.3	26.3

^a Mean of 3 replications. Observations recorded 80 days after transplanting (DT).

^b Plot size = 10.0 m², N applied in 3 equal splits at 4, 26, and 54 DT. Differences between varieties significant at 1%: LSD 0.05 = 3.1, LSD 0.01 = 4.4; between nitrogen levels, nonsignificant.

^c Plot size = 12.5 m². N applied in 3 equal splits at 4, 26, and 53 DT. All factors nonsignificant.

^d Plot size = 8.1 m². N applied in 3 equal splits at 5, 30, and 45 DT. Differences between varieties significant: LSD 0.05 = 3.8, LSD 0.01 = 5.5; between nitrogen levels, significant at 1%: LSD 0.05 = 5.5, LSD 0.01 = 7.3. Interaction nonsignificant.